

Community Guidelines Intervention Protocol MetaDocencia

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Objective	3
Scope	3
Principles	3
Intervention	3
Recording and Follow-up	5
About the Development of this Document	5

Objective

Establish a working guide for the team and the principles for acting in situations related to the Community Guideline (CG).

Scope

This protocol applies to all activities that are developed and organized by MetaDocencia or co-organized with other communities or individuals.

Principles

The principles that apply to situations and processes addressed by the CG team are:

a- Confidentiality: All information related to situations covered by the Protocol is confidential. We will protect the privacy and wishes of all individuals involved in the actions of the team.

b- [Conflict of Interest](#): If any member of the CG team is affected, the Management Team (MT) will be informed, and the affected member will be replaced until the situation is resolved.

c- Restorative Approach: We adopt measures compatible with restorative justice, such as encouraging dialogue, fostering empathetic attitudes, and supporting personal accountability processes. Those involved in a situation that has affected another will actively participate in the community intervention. We will avoid unnecessary repetition of the account of events and the public exposure of individuals or data that could identify them (principle of non-revictimization).

Intervention

The CG Team is responsible for acting and evaluating situations upon receiving communication at the email pdcc@metadocencia.org, according to the following steps:

1. Within two business days of receiving the email, the team will respond to the inquiry via the same channel or propose a meeting as soon as possible if necessary.
2. Once the situation is assessed, the CG team will analyze and propose a possible solution in accordance with the mentioned principles. The initiatives may include:
 - a. Internal warning. Request for public or private apologies.
 - b. Request for a meeting with the individual(s) to discuss the aspects of the Community Guidelines that were violated and how to learn from the mistakes.
 - c. Group activities, educational sessions on aspects of the CG, or dilemmatic situations that could motivate community and collective learning.
 - d. Expulsion from the community if the disrespect to the CG persists.
3. In cases where, despite the intervention of the CG team and when restorative practices are insufficient, specific actions or even expulsion from the organization may be suggested. For individuals who are not part of the organization but participate in MetaDocencia activities as part of the general community, actions may also include disqualification from participating in activities for a defined period.

In the event of unacceptable, extreme, and/or violent behavior that endangers those involved in an activity organized or co-organized by MetaDocencia, any member of the organization may act to mitigate the harm and support the individuals initially, with the commitment to notify the CG team as soon as possible through an appropriate channel.

4. In cases where no conflict develops, such as when a potential Conflict of Interest is not real, or if an authorship conflict is reported where the parties cannot agree but the differences are resolved amicably, respectfully, and following the CG, i.e., in cases that do not escalate to a CG report, the team will suggest gathering the parties to reach an agreement.

Recording and Follow-up

A record of all interventions by the CG team will be created and must include:

- A. Personal information of the consulting person.
- B. Description of the situation being consulted about.
- C. Evaluation of the situation.
- D. Observations and intervention strategies.
- E. Resolution given to the situation.
- F. Evaluation and follow-up of the proposed resolution

In cases where despite the intervention of the CG team, restorative practices prove insufficient, apologies, actions, or even expulsion from the community may be suggested.

About the Development of this Document

This document was generated within the framework of the Open Seeds 8 program by OLS.

This publication was made possible thanks to a grant from NASA 80NSSC23K0854 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8215455](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8215455) and grant DAF2021-239366 from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative DAF (Grant DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37921/522107izqogv>).

Did you like this post? You can freely reuse it under the license CC by 4.0; you just have to cite it.

This is the quote that we recommend you use to reference it: Laura Ascenzi, Paola Lefer, Romina Pendino, Iván Poggio, Verónica Xhárdez (2024). "MetaDocencia Community Guidelines 2024". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13237096>